

Experimental Characterization of Swirl-Stabilized Pulverized Fuel Flames: Impact of Oxyfuel-Atmospheres and Fuel Diversity

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Motivation

- Necessity for decarbonization
- Potential for negative emissions via BECCS: Bio-energy carbon capture and storage

Main targets

- What happens when replacing air by oxyfuel?
- What is the difference for a wide range of fuels, including biomass?

Methods

- 100 kW_{th} combustion chamber
- 400 mm inner diameter
- Electrically heated walls
- Self-sustained combustion
- Vertically displaceable burner
- Stationary measurement equipment
- Optical and probe access
- Measured quantities
- Particle Velocity (LDV)
- Reaction zone visualization (Narrow Band)
- Local particle temperatures (Spectral)
- Local gas composition (FTIR)

Two different burners:

Laser Doppler Velocimetry (LDV)

Narrow Band Imaging

- CCD camera with optical filter
- 308 nm for OH* chemiluminescence
- 430 nm for black body radiation

Initial results on coal and torrefied biomass

- 60 kW_{th} coal experiments, varying λ^* [2]
- momentum ratios at burner determine stabilization
- 60 kW_{th} coal experiments, varying O₂ in oxidizer (21 vs. 25 vol.%) [3]
- Increased O₂ content accelerates combustion and concentrates heat shift toward shorter hydrocarbons (CH₄, C₂H₂)
- Lower O₂ levels stretch the reaction zone and lower pollutant formation: lower peak temperatures, and reduced NO and SO₂ emissions.

- 60 kW_{th} coal experiments, air and varying O₂ in CO₂ in oxidizer (21 vs. 25 vol.%) [4]
- Conventional air-firing exhibited significantly higher particle temperatures and radiation intensities (order of magnitude) compared to both oxy-fuel cases
- The air case showed a well-defined local radiation peak, whereas oxy-fuel profiles were monotonic with no significant local gradients downstream.
- Coal particles acted as gray-body radiators, with atomic emission lines (Na and K) directly correlating to temperature trends; only localized soot influence.
- 40 kW_{th} coal experiments, increasing O₂ in oxidizer (23 vs. 25 vs. 27 vol.%) [5]
- Higher velocities in the main vortex, along with reduced and more localized recirculation
- More intense gas emission, boosting axial momentum and reducing the local swirl level
- 40 kW_{th} Torrefied biomass experiments compared to coal at similar flow conditions [6]
- Higher radiative heat flux, higher NO and CO levels in exhaust gas, similar flow fields

*here, λ denotes the ratio of oxygen available compared to as required for complete combustion

Recent experiments on ground walnut shell and CH₄ co-firing

- Influence of Methane Co-Firing [7]
- similar effect as early volatile release: its combustion generates significant heat flux towards particles, effects on flow field and heat release zones.

- Increasing thermal load [8]
- enhances flame stabilisation at diffuser, though role of momentum cannot be neglected here

- Oxygen availability near burner
- governs combustion intensity, shifting spatial location of volatile and thus heat release

Complementary reaction rates

- Fluidized bed reactor with subsequent Fourier-transformed infrared (FTIR) spectrometer:
- Enables determination of reaction rates for char [9] or pyrolysis kinetics [10] for solid fuels (or other solid material) in individually composed atmosphere
- Using data to model reactions of different complexity, e.g. chemical percolation devolatilization (CPD) vs. single first order reaction (SFOR) model

Results in brief

- Aerodynamically, the flame can be stabilized, when increasing the momentum of swirled oxidizer compared to that of fuel (straight)
- An early release or availability of volatiles and their ignition can have a similar effect as methane-co-firing: the effect on the flame flow field can even persist, when the available volatiles are reduced (e.g. when switching of a pilot flame)
- An early availability of oxygen especially effects the combustion in terms of the location and intensity of reactions, though the flow field can be less affected.

Literature:

[1] Zabrodiec, Diego, 2021, *Experimental characterization of turbulent particle laden reactive flows under air and oxy-fuel conditions*, PhD Thesis, doi:10.18154/RWTH-2022-02974

[2] Habermehl, Martin; Hees, Johannes; Maßmeyer, Anna; Zabrodiec, Diego; Hatzfeld, Oliver; Kneer, Reinhold, 2016, *Comparison of Flame Stability Under Air and Oxy-Fuel Conditions for an Aerodynamically Stabilized Pulverized Coal Swirl Flame*, J. Energy Resour. Technol (Journal of Energy Resources Technology) (138), 4, doi:10.1115/1.4032940

[3] Hees, Johannes; Zabrodiec, Diego; Maßmeyer, Anna; Pielsticker, Stefan; Gövert, Benjamin; Habermehl, Martin; Kneer, Reinhold, 2016, *Detailed analyzes of pulverized coal swirl flames in oxy-fuel atmospheres*, Combustion and Flame (172), 289-301, doi:10.1016/j.combustflame.2016.07.028

[4] Zabrodiec, Diego; Hees, Johannes; Maßmeyer, Anna; vom Lehn, Florian; Habermehl, Martin; Hatzfeld, Oliver; Kneer, Reinhold, 2017, *Experimental investigation of pulverized coal flames in CO₂/O₂- and N₂/O₂-atmospheres: Comparison of solid particle radiative characteristics*, Fuel (201), doi:10.1016/j.fuel.2016.11.097

[5] Zabrodiec, Diego; Hees, Johannes; Möller, Georg; Hatzfeld, Oliver; Kneer, Reinhold, *Pulverized coal swirl flames in oxy-fuel conditions - Effects of oxidizer O₂ concentration on flow field and local gas composition*, PROCI (37), doi:10.1016/j.proci.2018.06.163

[6] Zabrodiec, Diego; Maßmeyer, Anna; Hees, Johannes; Hatzfeld, Oliver; Kneer, Reinhold, *Flow pattern and behavior of 40 kW_{th} pulverized torrefied biomass flames under atmospheric and oxy-fuel conditions*, Renewable & Sustainable Energy Reviews (138), doi:10.1016/j.rser.2020.110493

[7] Özer, Burak; Zabrodiec, Diego; Kneer, Reinhold; Maßmeyer, Anna, 2023, *Experimental investigation of 40 kW_{th} methane-assisted and self-sustained pulverized biomass flames*, PROCI (39), doi:10.1016/j.proci.2022.07.112

[8] Özer, Burak; Kneer, Reinhold; Maßmeyer, Anna, *Pilot Scale Pulverized Solid Fuel Combustion Experiments*, In: (Hg.) 2026 - Clean Energy Conversion, doi:10.1007/978-3-031-98956-8_14

[9] Tarlinski, David; Pielsticker, Stefan; Kneer, Reinhold; Schiemann, Martin; Scherer, Viktor, 2026, *Char Conversion Kinetics*, In: Kneer, Pitsch et al. (Hg.) 2026 - Clean Energy Conversion, doi:10.1007/978-3-031-98956-8_3

[10] Pielsticker, Stefan; Freisewinkel, Erik; Böttger, Jannik; Cerciello, Francesca; Senneca, Osvalda; König, Dominik; Scherer, Viktor; Muhler, Martin; Eppler, Bernd; Kneer, Reinhold, 2026, *Pyrolysis Products and Kinetics*, In: Kneer, Pitsch et al. (Hg.) 2026 - Clean Energy Conversion, doi:10.1007/978-3-031-98956-8_2

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